

EFFECTS OF NATURAL AGEING ON SEED GERMINATION PERCENTAGE OF SOYBEAN

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MS Received: 09.08.2024; MS Revised: 20.10.2024; MS Accepted: 21.10.2024

MS 3254

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURE,)

Abstract

The present investigation was conducted at the Experimental Farm, Department of Agricultural Botany, VNMKV, Parbhani, Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, VNMKV, Parbhani, the Quality Control Laboratory, MSSC Ltd., Parbhani, and the Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, College of Agriculture, Golegaon, Hingoli, using soybean varieties MAUS-71, MAUS-158, JS-335, and MAUS-162. Natural ageing was studied by storing seeds under conventional (uncontrolled) storage conditions and evaluating them at intervals of 0, 60, 120, 180, and 240 days for seed quality and biochemical parameters. Observations on different seed quality traits, such as germination percentage, were recorded at regular intervals. The soybean variety MAUS-162 was found to perform better in terms of biochemical parameters, including malondialdehyde, superoxide dismutase, peroxide activity, protein, oil, and dehydrogenase activity.

Keywords: soybean, natural ageing, temperature

Introduction

Soybean [*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill] is an important oil crop belonging to the family Leguminosae, subfamily Papilionaceae, and genus *Glycine* L. Soybean plays a crucial role in agriculture and export, especially in times of energy crises and shortages. It has now become a significant oil and seed crop, offering a cost-effective alternative source of high-quality protein and cooking oil. Soybeans are rich in protein, carbohydrates, and fats, and are an excellent source of vitamins, minerals, and beneficial plant compounds such as isoflavones. With its high nutritional value, soybean has great potential as a particularly nutritious and protein-rich food.

Soybean seeds reach their maximum potential for germination and vigor at physiological maturity. However, the germination (viability) of soybean seeds is relatively short compared to other oil crops and often declines before sowing. This loss of germination is more severe in tropical conditions, like those in India. The environmental conditions in these regions make it challenging to maintain seed viability during storage. One of the key factors contributing to this challenge is the various biochemical changes that occur in soybeans during storage. Generally, more vigorous seeds can withstand high temperatures and humidity while still producing normal seedlings.

Field performance and seed storage capacity are closely related to seed vigor, which is negatively impacted by different aging periods and storage conditions. As soybean seeds are hygroscopic, they tend to absorb or lose moisture, which leads to various biochemical changes in the seeds during storage.

Materials and Methods

The present investigation was carried out with the aim of assessing the seed viability of plant species with high oil content and their germination after being stored and aged for a certain period. Based on the assessment of aged seed vigour, we can determine its field emergence capacity and the potential for forming vigorous, healthy plants that will be high-yielding.

The experimental material for the investigation consisted of four soybean (*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill) varieties, representing two maturity groups: MAUS-71 and MAUS-158 (early maturity group: 93-95 days), and JS-335 and MAUS-162 (late maturity group: 95-103 days) (Loeffler et al., 1988). The seed material was evaluated for different

seed quality parameters, such as seed moisture, under natural aging conditions. Seed quality parameters were assessed at 0, 60, 120, 180, and 240 days of storage.

Results and Discussion

The data on the effect of varieties and storage duration on the germination (%) of soybean seeds during natural ageing are presented in Table 1 and Figure 1.

It is evident from Table 1 that there was a significant effect of soybean variety on seed germination. The germination percentage decreased after natural aging in all four varieties (Table 1).

The highest significant germination percentage was observed in the variety MAUS-162 (93.66%), followed by MAUS-158 (89.66%), MAUS-71 (89.00%), and JS-335 (85.00%) at the start of the study. Germination percentage decreased slightly up to 60 days of storage, after which it declined significantly (Table 1, Fig. 1). After 120 days of storage, the germination rate decreased rapidly in all four soybean varieties. By 240 days of storage, germination fell below or close to the minimum seed certification standard in MAUS-158 (70.66%), MAUS-71 (69.66%), and JS-335 (69.33%), while MAUS-162 maintained a higher germination percentage (76.00%) compared to the other varieties.

The germination percentage decreased progressively with the extension of the storage period. Regardless of the soybean variety, germination percentage was significantly affected by storage duration. Similar results were reported by Singh et al. (1988), who observed that the germination rate declined with increased storage time. This trend has also been confirmed by Larcher et al. (1984), Vyas (1990), Tekrony et al. (1993), Nkang and Umoh (1997), and Sharma et al. (2009). This decline in seed quality can be attributed to the depletion of food reserves, reduced embryonic activity, and seed death caused by fungal invasion. Gupta et al. (1997) and Kabeer and Taligoola (1983) also observed that soybean germination decreased as storage time increased at room temperature.

These findings align with those reported by other researchers in various crops, including okra (Narwal, 1995), cotton (Meena et al., 1994), carrots (Narwal, 1995), and radish (Khan et al., 2005). Similar results were found in onions (Promila Kumari, 1994) and radish (Maskri et al., 2003).

Table 1: Effect of natural ageing on seed Germination percentage of soybean varieties

	0 DAH	60 DAH	120 DAH	180 DAH	240 DAH	Mean V
MAUS 71	89.00	87.67	80.20	74.67	70.67	80.44
MAUS 158	89.67	84.33	80.00	76.67	71.67	80.47
JS-335	85.00	83.67	80.00	76.00	70.33	79.00
MAUS 162	93.67	87.00	83.00	79.67	76.00	83.87
Mean D	89.33	85.67	80.80	76.75	71.42	

TABLE OF SEM, SED AND C.D.

Factors	C.D.	SE(d)	SE(m)
Factor(V)	1.14	0.56	0.40
Factor(D)	1.27	0.63	0.44
Factor (V X D)	2.54	1.25	0.89

Note V = Variety D= Day's after Harvesting

Fig. 1: Effect of Natural ageing on seed Germination percentage of soybean varieties

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